

Sample Name: Nanotalc

Material: Talc

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: Nanoshel

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 88% particles are <1 μm
- Particles have a sharp, flake morphology with squared corners
- $6.4 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- $11830 \pm 150 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- P, Ca, Al and Fe were the most abundant contaminants, all <500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
 - Contaminants total 1263 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_V : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D _v	D _N	N _w	A _w
2.9±0.04	1.8±0.07	1.0±0.03	0.65±0.00	1.1±0.03	0.65±0.00	6.4±0.4 10 ¹¹	11830±150

Morphology (using *Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)* provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Component	Concentration (µg/g)
P	406
Ca	307
Al	246
Fe	238
Cl	58
Ti	7
Zn	1

**Quantification calculated based on oxide structure, Mg and Si concentrations*